

Supplementary Tables 3.2, 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7

Table 3.2. Summary of repeat content of the *P. retropinna* and *P. turrubarensis* assemblies.

	<i>P. turrubarensis</i>		<i>P. retropinna</i>	
	Number of elements	Percentage of sequence	Number of elements	Percentage of sequence
SINEs	17257	0.4	11824	0.24
LINEs	47774	1.66	54591	1.99
LTR elements	12849	0.55	13769	0.47
DNA elements	314227	8.7	365650	10.51
Small RNA	2202	0.05	640	0.01
Satellites and Simple repeats	280364	1.75	250007	1.74
Low complexity	38518	0.29	36246	0.27
unclassified	182306	5.14	187407	5.63
total	895497	18.51	920134	20.83

Table 3.5. significantly overrepresented GO terms for positively selected genes in *P. retropinna*

GO biological process	fold enrichment	raw P-value	FDR
protein targeting to peroxisome (GO:0006625)	12.94	2.12E-06	3.36E-02
establishment of protein localization to peroxisome (GO:0072663)	12.94	2.12E-06	1.68E-02
protein localization to peroxisome (GO:0072662)	12.94	2.12E-06	1.12E-02
peroxisomal transport (GO:0043574)	12.57	2.54E-06	1.00E-02
peroxisome organization (GO:0007031)	11.14	5.35E-06	1.41E-02
nervous system development (GO:0007399)	2.16	2.76E-06	8.73E-03

Table 3.6. significantly overrepresented GO terms for positively selected genes in *P. turrubarensis*

GO biological process	fold enrichment	raw P-value	FDR
phosphate-containing compound metabolic process (GO:0006796)	2.26	3.44E-06	5.44E-02
phosphorus metabolic process (GO:0006793)	2.23	4.16E-06	3.29E-02

Table 3.7. Effect of distinct filtering steps on amount of duplicated segments passing the filtering, and genes present within these segments.

	<i>P. retropinna</i>		<i>P. turrubarensis</i>	
	Number of duplicated segments	Number of genes within these segments	Number of duplicated segments	Number of genes within these segments
<i>No filtering (raw overlapping chains)</i>	21880	863	17365	776
<i>After filtering for overlap length (>3kb)</i>	2947	360	2658	391
<i>After filtering for absence of paralogous sequences</i>	641	79	994	110
<i>After filtering for scaffold length >100kb</i>	629	74	710	25
<i>After filtering for read depth anomalies</i>	410	53	421	20
<i>After filtering for ancestral copy number (<i>P. reticulata</i> outgroup)</i>	151	29	102	4